

Infrared Spectra (cm⁻¹)

Table 2

Electronic Spectra in K.K. (ε)

Compounds	Asym. N-H	Sym. N-H	Amide I ν(C=O)	ν(C=N)	ν(C≡N)	ν ₁ NO ₂		ν ₄ NO ₂	
						Sym.	Asym.	Sym.	Asym.
Nicotinamide	3350	3180	1650	1400					
CoCl ₂ (N.A) ₂	3200	3150	1645	1410					
Co(NO ₃) ₂ (N.A) ₂	3300	3140	1645	1410					
Co(NCS) ₂ (N.A) ₂	3320	3160	1640	1410	2080	1250	1450		
NiCl ₂ (N.A) ₂ [†]	3310	3140	1650	1390					
Ni(NO ₃) ₂ (N.A) ₂	3285	3145	1655	1400		1270	1400		
Ni(NCS) ₂ (N.A) ₂	3315	3160	1650	1420	2100				
CuCl ₂ (N.A) ₂	3310	3150	1640	1420					
Cu(NO ₃) ₂ (N.A) ₂	3290	3160	1645	1400					
Cu(NCS) ₂ (N.A) ₂	3300	3155	1640	1410	2080	1260	1390		
Zn(NCS) ₂ (N.A) ₂	3310	3150	1650	1420	2100				

Electronic Spectra in K.K. (ε)

⁴T_{1g} → ⁴T_{1g}(P) ; → ⁴A_{2g}(F)

CoCl₂(N.A)₂ 20.6(19) 18.7(32)

CoBr₂(N.A)₂ 21(20) 18.9(28)

Co(NO₃)₂(N.A)₂ 20.8(19) 18.6(30)

Co(NCS)₂(N.A)₂ 16.3(1400)⁴A₂ ⁴T₁(P)

³A_{2g} → ³T_{2g}(F); → ³T_{1g}(F); → ³T_{2g}(P)

NiCl₂(N.A)₂ 8.9(8.5) 14.0(6) 25.0(20)

NiBr₂(N.A)₂ 8.5(9) 13.8(6) 25.2(19)

¹T₁(F) → ¹T₁(P)

Ni(NO₃)₂(N.A)₂ 15.0(180)

Ni(NCS)₂(N.A)₂ 14.8(160)

E → T₂

CuCl₂(N.A)₂ 14.5(75)

CuBr₂(N.A)₂ 14.8(85)

Cu(NO₃)₂(N.A)₂ 17.0(80)

Cu(NCS)₂(N.A)₂ 16.8(90)

structure, a bidentate nitrate group for nitrate complex and tetrahedral geometry for the thiocyanato complex which is corroborated by the respective magnetic moment values.

Ni(II) halide complexes give rise to three absorption bands, the band positions and intensity being typical of spin free octahedral complexes. Nitrate and thiocyanato complexes are blue in colour giving a single absorption band at 15.0 K.K. (ε=160), the other expected band being outside the visible region. Band intensity, its position and the magnetic moment suggests⁶ a possible tetrahedral environment for these two complexes.

Cu(II) halide complexes have one single broad absorption band around 14.0 K.K. indicating a tetragonally distorted octahedral structure. Though three transitions are expected⁷ as a result of splitting due to Jahn-Teller distortions. More often than not the three transitions appear⁸ in form of a single broad band envelope. Nitrate and thiocyanato complexes give rise to a broad band around 17.0 K.K. (ε=80) suggesting a probable planar structure⁹.

All the zinc complexes reported here have an octahedral stereochemistry on the basis of their analysis, conductance and infrared spectral data.

References

1. B. G. Ramsey and J. G. Grasselli, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1969, 3, 503.
2. C. D. Rao and B. K. Mohapatra, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.* (In press).
3. L.V. Kononov, I.S. Kaslennikova and V.N. Shemyakin, *Zh. Neorg. Khim.*, 1970, 15, 1993.
4. W. Zygumt, *Rocz. Chem.*, 1975, 49, 1069.
5. R. V. Biagetti, W. G. Bottjer and H. M. Haendler, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, 6, 379.
6. D. M. L. Goodgame, M. Goodgame and F. A. Cotton, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 83, 4161.
7. C. A. Agamber and K. G. Orrel, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1969, 897.
8. B. J. Hathaway, I. M. Proctor and P. Nicholls, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1968, 1978.
9. A. B. Lever, "Inorg. Electronic Spectroscopy," Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1968.

Chemical Investigation of Some Mangrove Species. Part. III : *Rhizophoraceae*, a Mangrove Family

S. GHOSH MAJUMDAR and GOURI PATRA
Department of Chemistry, The University of Burdwan,
Burdwan 713 104.

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A thorough investigation for secondary metabolites of Sundarban mangroves has been undertaken from the stand point of ecological study^{1,2}. In the present communication, triterpenoids characterised from four mangrove species belonging to four different genera of mangrove family *Rhizophoraceae* are described.

Literature survey did not reveal the presence of any triterpenoid constituents in these four genera. However, the presence of cyanidin chloride and unidentified leucoanthocyanin³ in *B. gymnorrhiza*; brugine alkaloid and its ester^{4,5} in *B. sexangula*; procyanidin⁶, several leucoanthocyanidins⁶, *D. catechin*⁶, leucocyanthoin⁷ in *C. roxburghiana* have been reported.

Plant materials for investigation were collected from Sundarban (West Bengal) in the month of December.

Petroleum extract of leaves of *R. conjugata* was taken up in ether and separated into neutral and acidic fractions by usual procedure¹. Each of the two fractions were then chromatographed, the former one directly and latter after esterification with diazomethane. The acidic portion yielded no triterpenic acid. The result of chromatographic separation of neutral fraction is given below.

First fraction was white crystalline solid, m.p. 166°, [α]_D+117° (C, 0.8); ν_{max} 1700 (carbonyl), 1650 cm⁻¹ (double bond); M.S. m/e 424 (M⁺), 409 (M⁺-CH₃), 218 (retro Diels-Alder fragmentation),

203 (218-CH₃), 189 (double hydrogen transfer from retro Diels-Alder fragment to form a highly conjugated allylic cation); NMR. (δ) 0.85-1.62 (methyl and methylene protons), 1.89 (vinyl-methyl protons), 2.35 (α-keto methylene at 2-position), broad m centered at 5.23 (proton at 12 position); λ_{max} 217 mμ; oxime m.p. 260°; LiAlH₄ reduction product m.p. 195°. All these data showed the presence of β-amyrone which was further confirmed by direct comparison with an authentic sample.

Second fraction was a mixture of triacontanol m.p. 80° and taraxerol m.p. 268°. Third fraction was β-amyrin m.p. 198° and the last one was β-sitosterol m.p. 135°. Each of them was identified through melting point, rotation, co-tlc and thorough spectral studies as described earlier¹. Other plants are analysed as before and the results of investigation of four investigated genera of family *Rhizophoraceae* are tabulated below.

TABLE 1.
Compound isolated (in gms)

Plant/source	Portion	Compound isolated (in gms)							
		A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
<i>R. conjugata</i> (Sundarban)	Leaves 1.5 Kg	0.05	0.50	x	0.70	x	x	0.01	0.10
<i>B. gymnorhiza</i> (Sundarban)	Leaves 3 Kg	5.00	x	x	6.00	x	x	1.00	0.70
<i>K. rheedi</i> (Sundarban)	Bark 2 Kg	1.00	x	0.02	t	x	x	0.04	x
	Leaves 1½ Kg	0.85	x	0.02	0.02	x	x	0.03	x
<i>C. roxburghiana</i> (Sundarban)	Bark 5 Kg	t	x	x	0.02	t	t	t	0.02
	Leaves 1.5 Kg	0.30	x	x	0.15	0.08	0.10	0.08	0.02

A=β-amyrin; B=β-amyrone; C=Friedelin; D=Taraxerol; E=Betulin; F=Betulinic acid; G=β-sitosterol; H=Triacontanol, t=traces by tlc.

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References

1. S. Ghosh Majumdar and G. Patra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1976, 53, 947.
2. Communicated to *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*
3. T. K. Seshadri and B. Venkataramani, *J. Sci. Ind. Res. (India)*, 1959, 18B, 261.
4. J. W. Loder and G. B. Russell, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1966, 51, 6327.
5. J. W. Loder and G. B. Russell, *Austral. J. Chem.*, 1969, 22, 1271.
6. T. R. Seshadri and R. K. Trikha, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, 9, 928.
7. D. Ghosh and S. K. Barat, *Chem. Abs.*, 1964, 60, 4351e.

Thermodynamic Stability Constants of Praseodymium(III), Neodymium(III) and Samarium(III) with Tyrosine.

RANJIT SINGH SANDHU and S. SINGH
Department of Chemistry, Guru Nanak Dev University,
Amritsar.

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Though there is a considerable information about formation constants of metal complexes of amino acids¹⁻⁴, little work appears to have been reported with tyrosine, a biological important molecule. In a previous communication^{5,7}, formation constants of lanthanons with tyrosine have been reported. In this note, thermodynamic stability constants of Pr³⁺, Nd³⁺ and Sm³⁺ with tyrosine are being reported.

Experimental

The protonation constant and successive formation constants were determined by Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti⁸⁻¹⁰. All chemicals used were either BDH or Aldrich AnalaR quality. The ligand solution was prepared in CO₂ free conductivity water immediately before use. The metal nitrate solutions were standardised by E.D.T.A. method. The thermostat bath temperature was maintained at 30° ± 0.1°. The mole ratio of metal to ligand was kept 1:5 in order to fulfil 'maximum coordination number of the metal. The three solutions (total volume 50 ml in each case) were prepared as follows:

A: 1.0 x 10⁻² M HNO₃

B: 1.0 x 10⁻² M HNO₃ + 0.25 x 10⁻² M ligand

C: 1.0 x 10⁻² M HNO₃ + 0.25 x 10⁻² M ligand + 0.5 x 10⁻² M metal nitrate.

An appropriate quantity of KNO₃ (1.0M) was added to maintain an ionic strength at 0.1, 0.2 or 0.3 M. The above solution, was titrated against carbonate free 0.1 M KOH solution. pH was measured on Photovolt digital pH meter having a sensitivity of 0.002 units.

The plots of pH versus the volume of alkali added were plotted. In calculations, concentrations were corrected for changes in volume produced by the addition of alkali during titration. The calculated error in stability constant is ±0.01 log K units. The shape of curves were as usual.

Results and Discussion

The proton ligand curve was obtained by plotting degree of formation (α_{H}) of the proton complex against pH value using the relationship derived by Irving and Rossotti⁹⁻¹⁰. The proton ligand stability constant (amino functional group)